

1 **Sox5 functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for Sox5 in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

11 Citations

12 1. Smits, P., Li, P., Mandel, J., Zhang, Z., Deng, J.M., Behringer, R.R., De Crombrughe, B. and
13 Lefebvre, V., 2001. The transcription factors L-Sox5 and Sox6 are essential for cartilage formation.
14 *Developmental cell*, 1(2), pp.277-290.

15 2. Lai, T., Jabaudon, D., Molyneaux, B.J., Azim, E., Arlotta, P., Menezes, J.R. and Macklis, J.D.,
16 2008. SOX5 controls the sequential generation of distinct corticofugal neuron subtypes. *Neuron*, 57(2),
17 pp.232-247.